

BIOCRISTALLOMICS IN PARASITOLOGY: CURRENT STATE, POSSIBILITIES AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract. The current state of biocrystallogics is given. The goal, objectives and main areas of study of biocrystallogics are presented. The main forms of biocrystallogenesis are systematized taking into account the functions they perform. The methodology for assessing the crystallogenic properties of various biosystems, including biological fluids, is described in detail.

Keywords: biocrystallogics, parasitoses, diagnostics, pathogenesis.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that many living organisms have the ability to form crystalline or pseudocrystalline bodies inside themselves and/or in the external environment. Thus, for agents of the microworld the latter option is predominant [1], whereas in higher organisms endolithogenesis prevails [2]. In addition, the interest of many researchers, primarily mineralogists, is attracted by the supposed “intermediate” role of crystals as intermediates of living and inanimate nature. This thesis is confirmed by long-term research by The most striking examples are the formation of bird eggshells, the presence and nature of sediments as a result of the activity of ice-forming bacteria, the formation of pearls by mollusks, etc.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

On the other hand, it should be noted that each of the above-mentioned theories, despite the observed tendency towards globalization (primarily with respect to the functional morphology of biological fluids), concerns only some particular patterns of formation of biogenic crystals. Thus, the concept of Shabalin and Shatokhina, based on the diagnostic value of individual marker structures generated as a result of dehydration of biological environments and, according to the authors, being highly specific indicators of specific pathological conditions, can be applied exclusively to the study of the biosubstrate’s own (without the participation of any chemical modulators) crystallogenesis [3]. The essence of Rapis’s theory is the prerogative of protein as an organizing principle in the processes of structure formation of drying droplets. This hypothesis is substantiated by the author and co-workers from an experimental-theoretical standpoint using methods of mathematics, physics, and physical chemistry [2], however, the information obtained by the developers cannot be directly extrapolated to biological objects, since the research conducted was carried out only on model systems “protein – water” [1].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Biocrystallogics is a science about the structure, properties, mechanisms and conditions of formation and degradation, as well as the functional significance of bio-associated crystalline and pseudocrystalline bodies.

The main goal of biocrystallogics as a new synthetic science should be a comprehensive, multifaceted interpretation of the nature and essence of crystallization associated with the vital activity of organisms. The range of primary objectives of the discipline may include:

1. Study of the structure and properties of biogenic crystals themselves;
2. Clarification of the mechanisms and conditions that ensure the formation of biocrystals;
3. Disclosure of the functional significance of the phenomenon in question;

4. Study of the information capacity of biogenic formations of crystalline and pseudocrystalline structure;

5. Assessment of the possibilities of adequate use of the information contained in biocrystals;

6. Consideration of the prospects and features of biocrystallogenesis management both in the external environment (in vitro) and inside the body (in vivo);

7. Disclosure of the general biological role of biogenic crystals.

As the most general parameter characterizing the initiating properties of a biological substrate or organism in relation to the entire set of potential basic substances, we propose the term "initiator potential" [4]. Its implementation for a specific basic substance (or their system) is the "initiator profile". The introduction of these concepts seems significant to us due to the fact that, as shown in the works of some authors [2] and in our previous studies, the initiator capacity of bioobjects varies significantly depending on the basic compound used. This is due to the fact that the introduction of various substances into the bioenvironment differentially changes the microenvironment of crystals, transforming the conditions for the occurrence of biocrystallization [1]. Therefore, the completeness of the extraction of the information capacity of the biomaterial is determined by the correct selection of the complex of basic substances (the initiated series). The last group includes a small number of methods that allow manipulations of varying complexity to be carried out with a drying biosystem. The methods of substrate congregation (according to G.G. Korotko, 2000) and model composites are based on isolated crystallization of individual components of biological media (proteins, lipids, carbohydrates, inorganic and organic salts) individually and in various combinations [1]. The approaches of experimental biocrystallography, initially being exclusively research, are designed to solve one of the most fundamental problems of the discipline – the development of methods for controlling biocrystallogenesis. In our opinion, such modeling and study of the influence of a wide range of modulators (physical, chemical, biological and mixed) of this process will allow the formation of experimental and theoretical foundations for targeted qualitative and quantitative modification of bioassociated crystallization [4].

CONCLUSION

Thus, by now the foundation for the formation and active development of a new discipline – biocrystallography – has been fully formed. At the same time, crystallographic methods for studying biological substrates of the human and animal organism currently represent a dynamic branch of knowledge capable of providing significant information for both experimental-theoretical and clinical (veterinary and medical) parasitology.

REFERENCES

1. Ashikhmin S.P., Zhdanova O.B., Maslennikova O.V., et al. Prospects for the Application of Crystallographic Methods for the Diagnosis of Alveococcosis in the Kirov Region // Russ. Parasitol. Journal. – 2011. – No. 1. – P. 94–99.
2. Barer G.M., Denisov A.B. Crystallographic Method for Studying Saliva. – Moscow: Federal State Educational Institution "VUNMC of the Russian Health Ministry", 2018. – 240 p.
3. Belova A.V. Microcrystal-optical Detection of Some Derivatives of Barbituric Acid in Forensic Medical Studies // Forensic Medical Examination. – 2010. – No. 2. – P. 37–45.
4. Buzoverya M.E. and others. Morphometric analysis of blood serum facies // Klin. lab. diagnostics. – 2013. – No. 9. – P. 22–23.